

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 3.3

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Booklet on overall stakeholder recommendations for the implementation of the future European Agroecology LL and RI Network

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Abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
AKIS	Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation System
D	Deliverable, e. g. D3.2
EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
LL	Living Labs
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCAR	Standing Committee on Agricultural Research
SWG	Agroecology Strategic Working Group
TP Organics	European Technology Platform for Organic Food and Farming
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work package

1. Executive Summary

The ALL-Ready project, funded by the European Commission, is a Coordination and Support Action aimed at establishing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs), from here referred to as 'future network'. This future network seeks to facilitate the transition to agroecology in Europe, addressing pressing challenges faced by farming systems such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and soil and water degradation. By engaging in transdisciplinary and participatory experimentation in real-life settings, the future network aims to promote knowledge exchange, provide valuable long-term ecological data, and support farmers in implementing agroecological practices at various levels. Through its focus on sustainability, resilience, and fostering positive economic, environmental, and social impacts, ALL-Ready strives to drive the widespread adoption of agroecology across diverse agricultural conditions in Europe.

Stakeholder engagement, a core aspect defined and developed in Task 3.1 *Stakeholder engagement coordination*, has been an integral part of all work packages within ALL-Ready. In this deliverable 3.3 (D3.3) we synthesise the outcome of the project's engagement efforts by drawing meaningful conclusions, in the form of lessons learnt. We employed a comprehensive two-step approach, utilising various sources of knowledge. We gathered direct feedback from external stakeholders, including regional workshop participants, pilot network members and consortium members, through surveys and interviews. Additionally, we extracted indirect feedback from project documents provided by consortium members. This approach facilitated the synthesis and evaluation of results, ultimately resulting in the formulation of 22 themed lessons learnt. These lessons, spanning both project and network levels, contribute to the future network's effectiveness and success in addressing significant challenges and opportunities. At the project level, lessons encompass stakeholder identification, timing and methods of engagement, content considerations and effective communication. At the network level, strategic elements such as governance structures, size, and refined project management approaches come into play.

Highlighted here are four key lessons that hold particular relevance for the future network. Nevertheless, we recommend the consideration and incorporation of all lessons, as they collectively offer comprehensive guidance and support for the future network's objectives.

LESSON 1: TAILORING CONTENT TO STAKEHOLDER NEEDS DRIVES OPTIMAL ENGAGEMENT emphasises the importance of aligning network activities' content with members' specific needs to foster meaningful connections and drive engagement.

LESSON 2: EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES ENHANCE EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT underscores the significance of clear and accessible communication when engaging external stakeholders.

LESSON 3: THE VALUE OF ROBUST EVALUATION IN STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT highlights the need for a well-structured evaluation process, with clear indicators for effective monitoring and evaluation of engagement activities.

LESSON 4: ADAPTABLE ENGAGEMENT FORMATS FOR ENHANCED STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT stresses the importance of diverse and flexible engagement formats to accommodate diverse preferences and overcome potential barriers.

Embracing these lessons is not just about improving our practices; it is crucial for the success and sustainability of the future network. Tailoring content, effective

communication, robust evaluation, and adaptable engagement formats form the cornerstones that will enable engaging stakeholders effectively, building trust, and achieving objectives. Our commitment to these lessons will support the continued growth and impact of the future network.

This deliverable is divided into the following chapters. Chapter 2 presents the theoretical background and methodological development of drawing conclusions from stakeholders' input for the future network. Chapter 3 explores the lessons learnt on the project level, while Chapter 4 focuses on the lessons learnt on the network level. Lastly, Chapter 5 reflects on the previous results by highlighting four specific lessons learnt and their relevance for the future network.

2. Developing lessons learnt from stakeholder engagement for the future network

Evaluation plays a crucial role in stakeholder engagement and particularly in the landscape of LLs. LL can foster ground-breaking innovation and development, but their success depends on internal and external variables (Schuurman et al., 2013). Such variables can be monitored and supported by introducing sufficient evaluation. The dynamic nature of LL benefits from set-backs and feedback, so that stakeholders can reframe their course of action accordingly (Veeckman et al., 2013). However, despite their wide implementation, LL are still understudied and lack performance evaluation (Bronson et al., 2021; Paskaleva & Cooper, 2021). Such evaluation can support tracking progress, promote longevity, and encourage meaningful engagement in the future network.

Therefore, task 3.3 of the ALL-Ready project responds to the calls for more evaluation by applying a lesson learnt framework, drawing on multiple sources. By evaluating the preparation phase of an agroecology LL and RI network we are supporting Bronson et al (2021; p.14) findings of “mov[ing] beyond particularity to make broader claims about the value of the approach” and pave the way for continuous improvement and long-term success in the future network.

2.1 Framing the evaluation process of stakeholder engagement

The overall objective of this deliverable is to reflect on stakeholder engagement developed in the ALL-Ready project and develop lessons learnt as a way to build the base for co-creation activities in the future network. We synthesise feedback received during the stakeholder engagement in ALL-Ready. In particular, this includes outcomes from the vision creation (WP1), the agroecology mapping (WP2), the stakeholder engagement planning (T3.1) and the pilot network (T3.2), the implementation planning (WP4), the capacity building (WP5), the knowledge and data management (WP6), and communicating and disseminating results (WP7).

Creating these lessons learnt ensures that agroecology LL, RI coordinators, national authorities, and facilitators of the future network receive insights that have been not only carefully thought out and planned but also tested in real contexts. The recommendations generated through this process were discussed and validated during the final pilot network meeting.

The stakeholder engagement plan (D3.1) defined four levels of stakeholder engagement, the types of stakeholders engaged and the stakeholder engagement objectives of each work package in the ALL-Ready project. The objective was to implement the stakeholder engagement plan while developing the framework for the future network. In order to achieve this, we adopted a **multi-stakeholder approach and involved end-users** from the outset. Stakeholders were defined for this document as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the project's objectives” (Freeman, 1984). Involving stakeholders throughout the process of defining challenges, good practice and recommendations for the future network served several purposes (D3.1):

- **Knowledge capture:** Engaging stakeholders allowed us to gather a diverse range of information and perspectives, incorporating their experiences, knowledge, and motivation. This has enriched our understanding and enables us to address stakeholders' needs more effectively.

- **Understanding diverse stakeholder values:** Different stakeholders hold diverse values, indicating that they have varying beliefs, priorities, and perspectives. These differences in values influenced how they assess the importance and value of the project and its objectives. The project aimed to acknowledge and understand these differing values in order to better address the needs and expectations of all stakeholders involved. This is also relevant in relation to the future network, given that it will encompass for example various European regions, capturing regional and local needs and conditions is crucial to ensuring responsiveness throughout all European regions.
- **Increasing ownership:** Engaging stakeholders in co-creation processes has fostered a sense of ownership, which is integral to the long-term success of the future network. Therefore, considering the durability of the network becomes one of the criteria for its overall sustainable success.

Evaluation plays a crucial role in measuring and enhancing the outcomes of stakeholder engagement activities. It involves comparing results with goals and distinguishes itself from planning or exploratory fact-finding endeavours, as Chevalier & Buckles (2019) explained. Throughout the ALL-Ready project, diverse stakeholders actively participated, aiming to foster knowledge production, sharing, a sense of ownership, and an understanding of the project's value. This engagement can take different forms and intensities. By evaluating and adjusting the engagement process, it has been observed that knowledge production improves (Louder et al., 2021; Mach et al., 2020), while also providing insights into the optimal degree, duration, and setting of engagement (Dekker et al., 2021).

Evaluation plays a pivotal role in agroecology, given the interplay of complex local ecological and societal factors. Agroecological practices are deeply rooted in the unique dynamics of local ecosystems and the intricacies of community interactions. Converting these diverse experiences into universally applicable recommendations holds immense significance (Nicholls & Altieri, 2018) as it not only fosters the broader adoption of agroecological practices but also can contribute to the development of open innovation spaces dedicated to agroecology. Moreover, agroecology extends beyond the mere transformation of farming practices; it signifies a profound shift encompassing knowledge, values, and beliefs (Rossi, 2020). Through rigorous evaluation, we can effectively capture and document these transformative journeys, providing valuable insights into the evolution of knowledge systems and values. This understanding is indispensable for offering the necessary support and resources to nurture and facilitate such transformative shifts.

First approaches have been used to **evaluate the activities of LLs**, including those focused on numerical scales and performance indicators (e.g., ENoLL, 2019; Schmittinger et al., 2020). However, in D3.3, a different approach was taken, based on the proposal by Overdiek & Genova (2021), to capture the diverse perspectives and experiences of stakeholders involved. The objective is to provide engaging and implementable learning inputs, prioritising implementable learning inputs (lessons-learnt) over managerial indicators traditionally used for performance evaluation. By adopting this approach, D3.3 aims to ensure that the knowledge and feedback from stakeholders will inform the future network in a meaningful way.

The final **lessons learnt** encompassed identified challenges, failures, and successes encountered during the project. This includes documenting problems faced, mistakes made, obstacles that hindered progress, as well as effective strategies, best practices, and actions that contributed to success. Actionable recommendations were provided to mitigate challenges and expand good practices in the future network. The lessons learnt were summarised in a condensed and communicable manner to ensure wide dissemination and practical utilisation. The primary audience for these lessons is facilitators of the future network, agroecology LL and RI coordinators, as well as national authorities, who can benefit from the evaluation and conclusions presented in this deliverable.

2.2 The Theory of Lessons Learnt

Lessons learnt are derived from a comprehensive process that incorporates successes, challenges, and incidents, integrating them into future frameworks (McClory et al., 2017). The knowledge produced through this process can have a profound impact, leading to changes in individual or organisational behaviour based on experiential learning (Milton, 2010). This crucial process plays a vital role in project and knowledge management, offering the ability to discern best practices and apply them to forthcoming endeavours, such as the prospective network. Various approaches, rooted in organisational theory, exist to define, and cultivate lessons learnt. In the following, two approaches of identifying and implementing a lesson learnt are combined to develop a robust process for reflection, enhancement, and practical application.

Learning a lesson can be described by Milton's (2010) theoretic learning loop containing three repeating phases: activity, identification, and instrumentalisation (darker grey in Figure 1). By first reviewing past activities in e.g., a project, one can identify learning points as positive or negative differences between expectations and outcomes. In the following analysis phase, stakeholders collaborate to take stock of these learning points, discuss their causes, and identify potential lessons. In the final phase these lessons are generalised for application in various settings, transforming them into lessons learnt. Based on these lessons learnt, future activities can be informed and updated to improve and learn from past experiences. This can help to avoid future pitfalls and to scale up successes. It is essential to first identify a lesson to then learn from it (lighter grey in Figure 1). This can be accomplished with a more applied approach, as outlined by Weber & Aha (2003). Their process starts with a collection phase, where lessons are gathered from multiple actors in various forms of information. Subsequently, the verification and synthesis phase assesses the applicability and validity of the lessons, taking into account their relevance to end users (i.e., members of the future network) and their impact on the organisation, project, or network (i.e., the future network). The lessons are then documented and stored for future use and access. Finally, the lessons learnt are disseminated by revising and redesigning processes based on the lessons.

Figure 1 The learning loop (adapted from Milton, 2010 and complimented with Weber & Aha, 2003)

Overall, by applying a lessons learnt process following the adjusted learning loop approach, the future network can benefit from and build upon the successes and challenges of the ALL-Ready project. However, it is vital to acknowledge that lessons learnt at the project level cannot be simply transposed verbatim onto the canvas of the future network's implementation. This is because the former is a project that includes a small-scale pilot

network, while the latter is envisioned as a large-scale network characterised by significant differences in resources and scope. Nevertheless, the process-orientated and organisational insights derived from stakeholder engagement in the pilot network and the ALL-Ready project can offer valuable recommendations for stakeholder engagement in the future network.

2.3 Methodology for developing lessons learnt

The future network will significantly impact and involve multiple stakeholders in practice, research, and policy. As each stakeholder possesses distinct knowledge and experiences from the project, which can influence various aspects of the future network, it is essential to incorporate feedback from these diverse stakeholders to support the future network.

To develop meaningful lessons learnt from the ALL-Ready project, a two-step approach was undertaken, considering different sources of knowledge. Table 1 shows the used methods of inquiry and the involved stakeholder group. Firstly, direct feedback was collected from external stakeholders who participated in regional workshops, pilot network members, and ALL-ready project consortium members. A survey was administered to regional workshop participants, resulting in 19 completed responses (see Appendix B), which shed light on their perceptions and experiences with the workshops and the network. Similarly, pilot network members were surveyed, with 10 responses received (see Appendix C), representing approximately 50% of the pilot network. Moreover, to gain deeper insights into challenges and best practices related to stakeholder engagement, interviews were conducted with the seven work package leaders between January and March 2023 (see Appendix D). In the second step, indirect feedback was extracted from ALL-Ready project documents. Consortium members also provided valuable learnings throughout their WP deliverables and in the workshop reports. By incorporating feedback from all these sources, the conclusions drawn from ALL-Ready will be more comprehensive and better aligned with the needs and expectations of various stakeholders. This, in turn, will aid in creating a future network that is more effective and successful in addressing relevant challenges and opportunities.

Table 1 Overview of used feedback sources to develop lessons learnt (own depiction)

Activity		Stakeholder type	Method of inquiry	Numeric return
Step 1: direct feedback	Survey with project external stakeholders	Representatives of Research, NGOs, Foundations, Governments, Farming, and the value chain	Feedback survey on-paper after two regional workshops	28
	Survey with pilot network member	Living lab and Research infrastructure coordinators	Feedback survey online sent to all pilot members	10
	Interviews with ALL-Ready work packages	ALL-ready work package leaders	Semi-structured interview in videocalls	7
Step 2: Indirect learnings	Project deliverables		Scanning and learning extraction from relevant deliverables	8
	Workshop reports		Scanning and learning extraction from workshop reports	4

Following the collection and scanning phase, results were synthesised and evaluated to derive lessons learnt. The synthesis aimed to extract concrete insights regarding the barriers, solutions, and best practices for the implementation of the future network. To achieve this, an inductive qualitative content analysis approach was used, following the framework introduced by Kuckartz and Rädiker (2019). During this phase, key themes relating to challenges and best practices were initially identified. These themes were subsequently distilled and enhanced based on the available data, as outlined in Appendix A. This analysis was conducted using the qualitative research software MaxQDA. To facilitate this process, a coding system comprising descriptive text labels was created, drawing from the challenges associated with stakeholder engagement that were originally developed in D3.1. This led to the formulation of 22 themed lessons learnt, which will be presented in the next two chapters. Figure 2 summarises the process of how the Stakeholders' feedback (dark blue arrows) on project activities (orange bubbles) lead to the development of two types of lessons learnt. The lessons learnt on stakeholder engagement at project level contain suggestions to improve the inclusion of relevant actors throughout the future network, based on the ALL-Ready project activities (light green arrows). The lessons learnt on stakeholder engagement at network level target directly the framework of engagement in the future network (dark green arrows). The aspects of these two lessons learnt sections are presented in detail in the following chapters 3 and 4.

Figure 2 Process of defining lessons learnt within ALL-Ready (own depiction)

3. Lessons learnt on stakeholder engagement at project level

In the upcoming subchapters, we will present the lessons learnt from stakeholder engagement at project level, generated in ALL-Ready which can be translated into the more operational sphere of the future network. Hereby five categories of lessons emerged:

- The stakeholder identification process, including the actual steps involved, the importance of incorporating a diverse range of stakeholders, and strategies for reaching out to individuals who may be difficult to engage.
- Methods of engagement adjusted to the different engagement levels, accompanied by offering incentives for taking part and identifying an adequate format.
- Early, frequent, and adaptable timing and frequency of engagement
- Alignment of the content of network activities with the specific needs and interests of its members
- Clear and accessible communication with internal and external stakeholders.

This section provides valuable insights into the substance of the activities and highlights key considerations for designing impactful engagement initiatives in the future network.

3.1 Stakeholder identification

In this section we focus on stakeholder identification process in the ALL-Ready project, highlighting challenges and lessons learnt. We discuss the diverse approaches used by different work packages and emphasise the importance of leveraging existing networks for identification. The chapter also addresses the need for inclusiveness, particularly in engaging policy stakeholders, hard-to-reach actors, and those who have not yet embraced the agroecology transition.

Stakeholders operate at different geographic levels, from regional to EU. They can be classified into different activities within the agroecology-relevant landscape, encompassing research, policy, farm advisory, the food value chain or citizen movements. Additionally, they can be identified as external or internal to the project or future network: Internal stakeholders include the (pilot) network members, ALL-Ready WP leads, the project coordination and project partners. External stakeholders encompass individuals and entities within the agroecological realm who express interest in joining the network, policy makers, sister projects, and the wider public. Appendix E lists all relevant stakeholders who participated in the ALL-Ready project and the WP's level of engagement with them.

3.1.1 Varied identification process

The work packages **employed different approaches to identify** the stakeholders they would engage with to achieve their work package objectives. For instance, they leveraged existing contacts and established networks within the agroecology field, such as the AKIS network and TP Organics, to enhance stakeholder engagement, or FACCE-JPI, a platform where stakeholders gather to organise funding activities related to sustainability issues in EU agriculture (WP7; WP2). On the other hand, WP2 strategically identified key informants from national authorities, recognising their role as key funders. WP5 focused on engaging with existing pilot network members to determine their capacity-building needs, recognising their relevance and effectiveness in terms of feasibility and methodology.

Tailoring the geographical focus in stakeholders to match specific needs in work packages has proven effective. Illustrating this concept, in the context of WP7, ALL-Ready centred its stakeholder engagement efforts at the European level, a strategic choice that streamlined data collection. Depending on the circumstances, it sometimes appeared to be

challenging to identify or reach the targeted stakeholder group for individual work packages. In the case of WP3 for instance, they targeted large networks spanning multiple countries. They were specifically approaching representatives with an overarching view of the network's activities, rather than sporadically engaging with individual stakeholders within LL or RI networks who may not have a comprehensive understanding of the overall picture. By implementing a top-down identification strategy, the project overall achieved widespread coverage across the entire geographic territory and established connections with influential stakeholders like the SCAR and Agroecology Strategic Working Group. In the pursuit of crafting a comprehensive Capacity Building Plan (D5.1), the consortium recognised the significance of addressing regional variations, prompting the need to customise and diversify the plan accordingly. This approach was deemed more advantageous than diversification based on variations among key end-user groups.

Another good practice is to foster **synergies across work packages**. WP4, for instance, built upon the survey conducted by WP1 and WP2 to identify relevant stakeholders for engagement. By doing so, LLs and RIs were identified as the primary target group for interviews conducted in Task 4.1. This target group was further expanded through a snowballing method, whereby invited stakeholders forwarded the invitations to their networks. Consistently following the snowballing method in the future network is recommended to consistently identify and reach relevant stakeholders.

3.1.2 Diversity and inclusiveness

Engaging a diverse range of stakeholders was a core focus for the ALL-Ready project, guided by the promise of mutual benefit and alignment with future network objectives. However, this endeavour was not without its challenges, which can be categorised into distinct areas, each with its own set of solutions and recommendations. Addressing these challenges and embracing the proposed solutions is paramount for cultivating a future network that thrives on inclusive, comprehensive, and effective stakeholder engagement.

Balancing **diverse perspectives and ensuring inclusivity** posed a significant challenge. The focus on specific groups like LLs and RIs within the agroecology landscape risked sidelining other valuable viewpoints from wider interest groups. This was especially evident in the scarcity of LLs in the pilot network with a specific policy and socio-economic focus, emphasising the need to incorporate these perspectives into the upcoming European network. Furthermore, the representation of farmer and farmers' association voices relative to researchers presented challenges in WP2, WP6, and WP1, underlining the necessity to increase their presence. The analysis of stakeholder types represented in regional workshop revealed underrepresentation of consumer and producer associations. Alongside, urban perspectives, including consumer-producer associations, food councils, and local neighbourhood initiatives are relevant to include more in the future network iterations. Efforts to engage policy stakeholders, despite collaborations with entities like SCAR, brought unique challenges. At times, opportunities for engagement were missed, such as those involving External Advisory Board members and other EU-level policy stakeholders (including EIP-AGRI, European experts, and organizations, as well as the CAP Network). Their input was rated as valuable and relevant to integrate these policy actors into the future network more effectively.

3.1.3 Engaging the hard-to-reach stakeholders

Incorporating hard-to-reach stakeholders poses a challenge but is also very important, as their insights and involvement contribute essential perspectives to the field of Agroecology and the future network. However, this endeavour is not without its challenges. An overarching challenge, as noted in WP4, is the identification and engagement of these

stakeholders. One effective approach is to initiate **discussions within existing stakeholder groups** to glean insights into the identity of hard-to-reach actors and the most effective methods to connect with them. This strategy, while productive, has its hurdles, given that local actors often possess more nuanced knowledge than external counterparts. Conducting a **targeted stakeholder analysis** presents another possibility, including addressing central queries such as: "Which groups of actors benefit from the transition?" or "Which stakeholders lack adequate representation despite being impacted by agricultural policy decisions?"

The task of reaching out to **actors who have yet to embrace the agroecology transition** poses another challenge, highlighted by WP2. The focus of ALL-Ready activities leaned towards stakeholders already involved in organising LLs centred on organic production or similar alternative agricultural practices. However, this concentration potentially sidesteps stakeholders with significant influence in sectors that require a transition, despite the inherent difficulty in engaging them. Looking forward, a key challenge for the future network lies in actively involving stakeholders who might remain unconvinced about the Agroecology Partnership and the network's value, as emphasised in WP1. WP2 underscores the need to enhance communication methods and styles to bridge this engagement gap (refer to Ch. 3.5).

3.2 Methods of engagement

The project encompassed different activities of stakeholder engagement aligned with the different work packages. They range from informing, where stakeholders are updated without intervention opportunities, to consulting with offered options and feedback but no new ideas, involving for joint decision-making and additional ideas, and collaborating through forming partnerships for joint decision-making and implementation. A learning from overall stakeholder engagement is to draft a project or network-wide engagement plan, as issued in D3.1 as this allows to identify utilisation of different stakeholders' expertise. The different engagement levels offered various advantages, including the ability to stimulate involvement and inclusion, create a feeling of ownership, and enable measurement and evaluation. In future network's co-creation initiatives these strengths should be fully utilised. This chapter lays out the different relevant aspects and learnings for the different levels of engagement, which were identified in D3.1. Appendix E lists all relevant stakeholder types and the WP's level of engagement with such. Further, recommendations are given regarding the importance of incentives for engagement, and considerations in choosing the format of engagement, including the balance between in-person and online activities.

3.2.1 Level of engagement

(1) Collaboration

Considering that collaboration and co-creation processes are intricate and time-intensive, the **co-design method is recommended for collaborating** with a similar-sized group within the future network. While co-creation played a pivotal role in the pilot network, particularly during collaborative activities (WP3), it was often replaced with co-design, especially during evaluations or the conceptualisation of network expectations and benefits. Rather than commencing from scratch, initial inputs were presented at pilot network meetings, allowing participants to contribute, revise, and provide comments. Due to limited resources and time in the ALL-Ready project's WP3, establishing and operationalising a comprehensive co-creation process for all activities proved challenging. Additionally, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic initiated online co-creation activities, constraining the initial engagement of pilot network members. Consequently, co-design emerged as the preferred engagement method, notably also for other WP-related processes like joint network activities and action plan development, encompassing aspects such as the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and the formulation of competences for the Capacity Building Programme (WP5).

When implementing co-creation methodologies, WP3 recommends a schedule of minimum three in-person meetings annually, supplemented by online meetings (WP3). Furthermore, it advocates not only involving stakeholders in the overall conceptualisation of joint network activity objectives but also in every incremental step of the process. An exemplary instance of successful co-creation, also serving as a platform to identify diverse co-creation methods, is the learning roundtable series, initiated during the second pilot network meeting. This series transcended the exchange of pilot network experiences and instead aided members in collaboratively devising solutions. During these discussions, challenges inherent in stakeholder co-creation were recognised, spanning from declining motivation and long-term engagement to divergent needs, expectations, and technical limitations. The proposed solutions encompassed transparent communication of mutual benefits, expectations, and added value, coupled with regular evaluations. Additionally, fostering a network's strength and enabling enduring cooperation entails creating avenues for members to connect and collaborate beyond the network's immediate scope.

WP7 proactively fostered collaborations with external ongoing initiatives, strategically aligning and consolidating efforts. This inclusive approach extended to engagements with prominent European-level networks dedicated to agroecology, notably the AKIS network and TP Organics, alongside close cooperation with the SCAR. This close collaboration materialised in the joint development of an organic Living Lab report within the context of the Organic Innovation Days. Persisting with this approach in the future network's framework would sustain such synergies.

(2) Involvement

Involvement, which fosters the generation of additional options and ideas while providing a platform for collective decision-making, stood as a cornerstone principle within the ALL-Ready project. Evidently, this level of engagement was utilised by each work package, where a consistent pattern of at least involvement or close collaboration with the pilot network emerged.

This participatory approach found profound expression in the iterative refinement of the agroecology framework (WP1) by involving external stakeholders from the SCAR (Standing Committee on Agricultural Research) Agroecology Strategic Working Group (SWG), who partially also participated in its co-design process, resulting in its enhanced quality and its potentially practical application within the future network. To enhance the engagement and expertise of pilot network members, WP5 organised workshops and training sessions, starting with an online workshop, and followed by an inaugural in-person gathering in Ghent, July 2022. To offer first-hand insight, a field excursion was arranged for pilot network participants, allowing them to visit the experimental fields of the Hansbeke-based Living Lab in Belgium. This initiative continued with a subsequent workshop in Budapest, complete with a field visit to the ÖMKI Living Lab in Szár, November 2022. Last, the pilot network gathered for a workshop in Montpellier, France including getting to know Occitanum Living Lab. These workshops **effectively collected data on specific requirements and conducted training for pilot members, focused on co-creation methodologies and related subjects.** The insights gathered from these training endeavours could be integrated into the development of a comprehensive capacity-building program for the prospective network. An assessment of the conducted WP5 training sessions will be incorporated in Deliverable 5.3.

(3) Informing and Consulting

This mode of engagement has emerged as the most frequently employed approach throughout the ALL-Ready initiative, in terms of numerical frequency (D3.1, Appendix E). Networking events, notably exemplified by regional workshops, played a pivotal role in cultivating novel connections among stakeholders and nurturing robust involvement within the network. Demonstrating alignment to this principle, WP7 maximised the opportunity presented by the Annual Meeting of the Global Forum for Rural Advisory Services (GFRAS) in

Serbia. In this context, their efforts transcended the mere dissemination of information pertaining to ALL-Ready and the Agroecology Partnership. WP7 actively leveraged this platform to not only disseminate information about ALL-Ready and the Agroecology Partnership but also to engage external stakeholders in meaningful consultations, **actively seeking their valuable insights and feedback**. This concerted interaction not only strengthens engagement but also underscores the project's commitment to cultivating a collaborative and informed network which will benefit the future network's position.

3.2.2 Incentivising engagement

To ensure active and sustained engagement from stakeholders joining the future network, thoughtful **consideration of financial incentives becomes paramount**. While ALL-Ready's pilot network participants were granted reimbursements for their travel expenditures, remuneration for their professional expertise was not included. Considering that members may be required to participate in multiple in-person meetings per year, it is recommended to provide appropriate compensation for their involvement. Within the pilot network, already a notable majority of members displayed robust engagement, suggesting that supplementary compensation might effectively incentivise also the remaining more inactive members to elevate their participation.

Financial allocations play a crucial role in enhancing stakeholders' and members' motivation and resource allocation for engagement. Nevertheless, it is essential to acknowledge that factors such as **knowledge dissemination, skill exchange, and fostering robust networking** can substantially sway an individual's view on participation. The establishment of a future network provides a unique platform for members to transition from practice-based thinking to system thinking, thereby offering a fresh perspective on their activities and strategic focus.

During the first pilot network meeting, some members voiced concerns about their sole role in providing data, a concern reminiscent of prior network experiences. Addressing these concerns needs effective communication that **highlights tangible value additions for members**. By accentuating the transformative prospects extended by the network—such as liberation from the confines of mere data provisioning—members can be motivated to actively engage and contribute their insights and expertise. It is important to underscore the several advantages of engagement, not solely for the network itself but also for individual members and their own undertakings. Participation in the future network will present opportunities for personal and professional growth, expanded networks, and enlarge skills and knowledge. Through active involvement, members are able to strengthen their personal endeavours while harnessing the collective expertise and resources of the future network.

Another valuable lesson from the ALL-Ready project is the need to plan and involve network members in dissemination activities (WP7). The specific methods for engagement could be determined during the development of the future network. Potential recommendations could include equipping members with communication and dissemination tools, assigning them the **role of ambassadors**, and providing monetary compensation as incentives for their participation. These strategies can enhance the involvement of network members and maximise the impact of dissemination efforts.

3.2.3 Format of engagement

Actively involving stakeholders can be achieved through various formats. The choice of engagement format depends on the cause, the type of stakeholders, accessibility, or desired level of participation. Before **choosing a format of engagement**, it is important that facilitators investigate and address potential barriers to engagement. These can involve aspects such as time and capacity restraints, inadequate inclusion and involvement, and complexity of methods. Efforts to overcome these challenges would enable an increase in active participation, proper data management, and a positive co-creation experience (WP3).

When being asked about productive elements within meetings, pilot network members highlighted the hands-on nature of the sessions with co-creation tools and methods, especially when participants brought their own experiences and challenges to the discussion. They also mentioned webinars, practical exercises, and field visits during pilot network meeting as engaging formats. There is potential for improvement in providing more activities that facilitate connections among scientists, particularly for building future research consortia.

Balancing professionalism and enjoyment in the sessions was found to increase engagement and foster an enjoyable and comfortable atmosphere for members and facilitators (WP3). The small group size and the facilitated relaxed atmosphere was also deemed as good practice by participants in the regional workshops. Moreover, breakout group discussions could be used strategically to spark more conversations and make sure everyone has an opportunity to contribute, as stated in the Budapest pilot network meeting report.

The COVID-19 pandemic necessitated a shift to **online meetings**, which had an impact on interactions within the pilot network. Compared to in-person meetings, pilot network members encountered difficulties engaging in an online format (WP5). In the pilot network evaluation survey, they stated that the online format limited their ability to feel “part of a network”. There was a higher barrier to asking questions online, as compared to a setting where all members are physically present in a room. Similarly, when co-creating the VRE, it was found that engaging key users involved in the co-design was easier in a face-to-face setting rather than online (WP6). While online tools, such as surveys and digital white boards (e.g., Mural), can be of great use when seeking experts’ advice, WP2 experienced the hesitation of knowledgeable experts of LLs and the RI landscape to fill out the form, due to time constraints, lack of incentives and lack of accessibility to online tools. A prior assessment of the tools and the directive target group can help the process of finding the right format.

However, there were also positive aspects of the digital format. It enabled regular meetings to take place despite the challenges posed by the pandemic. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that in-person meetings allow for longer and more comprehensive discussions. Generally, a good balance between online and in-person activities is desired (WP3). To compensate for the limitations of online meetings, a good practice was to increase the number of iterations, ensuring thorough collaboration and output when in-person meetings were not possible (WP1).

3.3 Timing and frequency of engagement

This chapter delves into the significance of timing and frequency in stakeholder engagement. It emphasises the importance of initiating collaboration early on, conducting timely stakeholder workshops, and striking a balance between project milestones and flexibility. The chapter also highlights the benefits of regular and frequent engagement with core network members, the need to avoid lengthy gaps between iterations, and tailoring the frequency of engagement to different stakeholder types.

Timing of engagement: early and adaptable

Timing is crucial in stakeholder engagement: It is highly recommended to initiate collaboration and engagement with identified stakeholders as early as possible. Stakeholder workshops serve as a valuable platform for realistic discussions and enable on-the-ground actors to express their perspectives on challenges and potential facilitators (WP2). Therefore, conducting stakeholder workshops within the first two months of the ALL-Ready project would have been more effective. Starting the stakeholder engagement process earlier would have also allowed for a third set of regional workshops to address the challenges faced by LLs and RIs and explore potential solutions (WP4). If the first set of regional workshops had taken place earlier, the objective could have shifted to identifying the stakeholders who could

have been more actively involved. It is beneficial to allocate sufficient time and planning to the preparation and invitation process of workshops to ensure flexibility in terms of timing (WP4). In WP6, there was time pressure at the beginning of the project to deliver an output. In hindsight, they found it would have been more effective to include the key end-user group from the project's inception rather than adjusting the timeline by delaying the involvement of pilot members (e.g., from Month 3 to 13). From the perspective of pilot network members, the outreach for feedback and input to project activities was rated as 'timely' and 'professional', showing they did not feel overwhelmed or pressured by the WP leads and activity facilitators.

Another aspect of timing to consider is the degree of flexibility and adaptability in stakeholder engagement. WP7 advises against overplanning, as each stakeholder has their own timeline and constraints. Overplanning can become a hindrance, so flexibility in specific dissemination actions may be encouraged to foster cooperation with other stakeholders. Striking a balance between project milestones and deadlines is essential. Investing a small amount of time and effort in the early stages can yield long-term benefits, even if the collaborative opportunities may not be immediately clear during initial contact.

Therefore, the WP leads strongly recommend initiating stakeholder collaboration from the very beginning, involving them frequently, and co-creating or co-designing outputs that are highly relevant. A recommended interval of five months between stakeholder workshops helps maintain momentum in discussions without overwhelming stakeholders (WP4). However, it is important to incorporate flexibility in the planning of activities to accommodate unforeseen circumstances (WP7).

Frequency of engagement: regular, frequent but stakeholder type-adjusted

Regular and frequent engagement with a core group of network members is highly recommended, especially for the co-creation of practical solutions. Working with a consistent group allows for frequent engagement and the opportunity to witness the evolution of ideas over time, making it an effective approach for the future network (WP5). Additionally, WP7 emphasises the value of maintaining longstanding communication within the pilot network. Building a strong network and building trust require sufficient time, a high level of activity, and intensity to foster meaningful developments. The process of transitioning from abstract discussions to practical solutions requires a steady flow of dialogue, which takes time to cultivate and is advised to be considered. In hindsight, an additional round of regional workshops could have been beneficial. This second round could have been divided into two discussions, with the first focused on generating potential solutions and an intermediate step for reflection and feedback, followed by a second discussion to address practical implications such as responsibilities, timing, and objectives (WP4). WP3 also recognised the need for more frequent pilot network meetings to achieve the objectives of joint co-creation activities. For the future network, WP3 recommends that members meet in person at least three times a year for co-creation activities, with online meetings in between. During the design of the VRE, pilot members played a crucial role in reshaping the product to better align with their specific needs. However, WP6 suggests incorporating additional rounds of iteration in the future network and increasing engagement to enhance the quality of results. Lengthy gaps between iterations have a detrimental effect on stakeholder involvement and activity (WP6), so it is important to avoid prolonged intervals between iterations. This finding is also supported by the answers from the pilot network survey, stressing the need for additional physical interaction between meetings for pilot network members to feel "part of the network".

Nevertheless, it is beneficial to tailor the frequency of engagement to the specific type of stakeholder. Actors who are consulted frequently are at risk of stakeholder fatigue (WP1, WP5). For example, WP1 had a single meeting with the external advisory board, although more meetings could have been planned. However, considering that these actors are extensively consulted, it is important to be mindful of their capacity and avoid overburdening

them. On the other hand, a different group of stakeholders indicated a differing willingness and capacity for engagement. Stakeholders from the regional workshops, organisations that are interested in becoming a part of the network, wished for more input prior to the meeting, for increased participation and generally higher frequency of meetings.

3.4 Content of activities

To optimise engagement within the European network, it is critical to align network activities' content with members' needs. Recognising this relevance, moving forward, it is important to observe challenges and respond to them promptly.

In light of this imperative, findings from the pilot network evaluation survey unveiled a challenge warranting attention. Pilot network members explicitly articulated the need for enhanced connections and **practical applications of agroecology within capacity-building activities**. With an eye on the future network, a recommendation emerges - infuse capacity-building sessions with a pronounced contextual link to agroecology, supplemented by real-world examples drawn from the agriculture sector. This transformation needs a multidimensional lens that takes into account key considerations. Who forms the core audience? What facets of stakeholders are represented in the network's activities? What nuances of interests and requisites define these stakeholders? Incorporating the design of capacity-building content with these insights holds the promise of yielding positive impacts on engagement levels. For example, envisaging interactive activities centred around tackling challenges and enacting measures to propel the agroecological transition forward, or introducing topic-focused workshops addressing specific hurdles like resource constraints and water sustainability, could effectively resonate with diverse stakeholders.

Extending this discourse, it was advised to **adapt the content of activities to the type of initiative** (LLs vs. RIs). This targeted tailoring, customising the content to fit the specific needs of each initiative, can enhance the overall engagement experience. The feedback from the evaluation survey highlighted a common perception among pilot network members. They noticed a particular emphasis on capacity-building content related to setting up LLs. On the contrary, LLs expressed a keen interest in the process of facilitating interactions, while RIs displayed a greater preference for in-depth discussions about specialised agroecological topics. Furthermore, it's crucial to acknowledge the inherent variety within the clusters of LLs within the network, which are characterised by diverse stakeholder participation. This underscores the need to tailor capacity-building content to suit these specific audience segments. This approach becomes especially vital as it could lead to content tailored for farmers taking on a significantly different format compared to content designed for municipal policymakers.

To ensure stakeholder interests are adequately represented, **engaging representatives from key stakeholder groups**¹ in the planning of content becomes imperative. These representatives are expected to advocate for the perspectives of their respective network members (WP3), infusing inclusivity and comprehensive representation into the content creation process.

3.5 Communication

The main lessons learnt on communication strategies in the ALL-Ready project relate to the use of accessible terminology and contextual framing when communicating with external

¹ A stakeholder group comprises stakeholders who operate within a shared "domain of activity". While the term "domain" lacks clear delineation, it could be interpreted as a distinct undertaking or focus area, such as policy, farm advisory services, the food value chain, and civic advocacy.

stakeholders, the importance of continuous internal communication mechanisms, and the need for collaboration across work packages and with other initiatives to optimise stakeholder engagement and dissemination activities.

3.5.1 Communication about the future network towards external stakeholders

When communicating with external stakeholders about the future network, it is crucial to use accessible terminology and an appropriate tone, while framing the information in a context-specific and relevant manner.

The use of **clear and accessible terminology** is important. In the online survey (WP2), external stakeholders highlighted that the use of overly complex and abstract terminology hindered their participation. Instead of exclusively using the term 'agroecology,' which is a specialized term in both science and policy, it proved advantageous to communicate with external stakeholders using terms like 'green transition in agriculture.' This more accessible phrase enables a wider audience to understand and engage, as it better aligns with the knowledge levels of various stakeholders.

Moreover, agroecology is highly context-specific, with distinct challenges and opportunities in different regions. Consequently, communication about the agroecology transition and the partnership must be tailored to the specific context. Generally, it is recommended to initiate communication with external stakeholders as early as possible (WP4). Furthermore, the concept of LL methodology is often poorly understood, so providing examples can significantly improve stakeholders' comprehension (WP7). Lastly, conveying a clearer message about the European network, including concrete metrics, fosters a stronger willingness for engagement from various initiatives. In addition to the choice of terminology within a meeting setting or publication, good practice such as adequate repetition of concepts and facilitation instruction, can accelerate access to the topic and ultimately to the network, as observed by participants in the regional workshops, who are external to the project.

Engaging stakeholders effectively in network development requires a **clear articulation of the benefits** they stand to gain. Without a perceived added value, sustainable involvement becomes challenging. Therefore, fostering long-term engagement necessitates aligning network objectives with stakeholder interests.

To overcome the language and terminology challenges associated with EU-wide communication and to effectively reach farmers, a **well-defined communication strategy** is essential (WP2, WP7). Drawing lessons from the ALL-Ready experience, dissemination activities may be planned in more detail better for the future network (WP7). One recommendation is to assign the task of communicating network activities to each partner, either in addition to or instead of the designated communication team. Additionally, all members of the network may have the responsibility to disseminate information at their respective levels (EU, national, local, urban, or rural), leveraging their own national language and networks while considering their specificities (e.g., extension services vs. scientific bodies). Providing tools, utilising network members as ambassadors, or offering monetary compensation are possible strategies to engage network members in dissemination activities. Allocating sufficient time and resources in budget planning, as well as ensuring qualified staff, is a prerequisite for successful communication.

3.5.2 Communication internal to the future network

It is important that the future network **incorporates mechanisms that ensure continuous communication** among members as this would provide network members with ongoing opportunities to engage, contribute, and express their views beyond formal meetings and newsletters. One effective approach could be the implementation of regular online

meetings in the form of jour fixe format to address specific issues and follow up on ongoing discussions.

When communicating with members of the future network, accessible terminology can facilitate common understanding. In the ALL-Ready project, for example, this was particularly important in the context of IT terminology within the VRE to enhance the understanding of end-users (WP6). Accessible terminology is also required in co-creation activities to align messages and terminology between users and network managers. Another good practice is the creation of a glossary for enhancing a common understanding on terms such as agroecology in general, LLs, RIs and other related subjects (WP5). This alignment promotes mutual understanding, consistent communication, and the ability to effectively address user needs.

3.5.3 Collaboration across work packages and with other initiatives

Effective implementation of stakeholder engagement activities in the future network will depend on communication within the network coordination team. A learning from the ALL-Ready project is to **extend collaboration with relevant initiatives**, such as the sister project AE4EU, to prevent stakeholder fatigue and use synergies in pursuing the common goal of an agroecological transition. Also, the internal communication between partners sometimes lead to missed opportunities for synergies and joint stakeholder engagement activities. To address this, it is important to maintain and where necessary increase the connection and understanding between work packages, which can be translated to the coordinating entities in the future network. A good practice is to routinely assess whether all pertinent network entities and stakeholders have been consulted and leveraged for specific activities. For instance, one might inquire whether the two relevant network entities have already exchanged knowledge on a similar topic and if input from particular network stakeholders is required for a network activity.

In order to establish a shared understanding of objectives and activities, **clear internal communication** needs to be established within the future network. Otherwise, there is a risk that ineffective internal communication of research findings and network activities leads to insufficient or untargeted external communication. Strengthening internal cooperation, especially concerning social media and other communication channels, is a key recommendation for the future network, including a continuous feedback loop between generated and shared information (WP7). Clear communication needs to be established around expectations, objectives, and methods to prevent delays in collaboration between the future network and external parties. This was observed in the communication with ALL-Ready and AE4EU: After some communication gaps, additional meetings have been scheduled to facilitate closer collaboration between both projects, particularly in the context of the final conference, to enhance the visibility of both efforts and use of synergies (WP7).

4. Lessons learnt on stakeholder engagement at network level

This chapter presents the key lessons learnt at the network level, drawing on the experiences and insights from the ALL-Ready project which relate more to the strategic sphere of the future network. Lessons emerged within the thematic fields of:

- Governance aspects of the network, such as its structure, size, and decision-making processes, and suggestions for establishing an effective and inclusive governance framework.
- Project management aspects of the network, such as resource allocation, objective formulation, and stakeholder engagement evaluation.

These lessons aim to guide the successful implementation and management of the network, as well as to enhance its sustainability and impact.

4.1 Governance of the network

This section explores aspects related to the future network's governance, including its structure and size, offering insights based on the experiences of the ALL-Ready project.

4.1.1 Structure and Size of the network

The existing network structure has proven successful in fostering stakeholder engagement, yet there is potential for future improvements and expansions in the network's structure. The structure of the pilot network proved to be a successful approach to foster stakeholder engagement and is recommended to be replicated in the future network. This included a limited number of members with different characteristics (RI or LL), geographical representation (Northern, Southern, Western, and Eastern Europe), scope of activity and maturity level. However, there is potential to enhance cooperation and promote place-based agroecology innovation by introducing additional structural components. to elevate cooperation and place-based agroecology innovation. One suggestion from pilot network members to facilitate solution-oriented exchange was the **creation of thematic working groups** within the future network. These working groups were not feasible to implement in the pilot network due to time constraints and limited capacities, but they can play a valuable role as operational bodies in the future network. Another possible addition could be the **introduction of regional clusters** as this would allow for a more representative and inclusive coverage of the EU regions (about 300), which influence the regional agroecology transition due to its regional or local specifications. Additionally, it was suggested that the future network could incorporate or **collaborate with major thematic networks at the national level**, addressing challenges related to the limited number of members and therefore coverage of expertise (see also Ch. 4.1.2).

Moreover, the network's size plays a critical role in determining the success of stakeholder engagement and collaboration efforts balancing a large diversity while remaining a more intimate size to comfortably exchange pose a challenge here. In chapter 3.1.2 we pointed out the importance of including diverse stakeholders which automatically would need a larger network. However, working with larger groups comes with trade-offs in terms of narrowing the scope to a specific set of stakeholders while excluding others. It is advisable to **organise the larger pool of stakeholders within the future network into smaller, more focused entities**, typically comprising 15-25 participants. This approach fosters more meaningful and productive discussions and cultivates a more intimate and trusting environment, as smaller groups tend to foster a strong sense of ownership and stakeholder

involvement. On the other hand, it would still allow for a larger and diverse network. The smaller units could also be achieved by introducing the mentioned thematic working groups and regional clusters.

However, the future network will have a larger size, should remain over many years and is therefore subject to changes in size. Past experiences have also underscored the complexities of effectively engaging with expansive networks spanning multiple countries, as mentioned in WP3. Adopting the approach of **commencing with a limited number of participants and gradually expanding** the network size proved to be well-suited within the context of the ALL-Ready pilot network and is recommended for the future network. From a coordination perspective, it is important to note that **engagement methods need to be tailored to the group size**. For instance, within the pilot network, WP3 effectively engaged smaller groups to develop organisational structures and engagement strategies for various members during learning roundtables, guided by LL and RI coordinators. With a larger group this would have been challenging as narrowing down the thematic scope to the involved stakeholders is rather difficult in a large and diverse group.

4.1.2 Institutional environment and Funding

Securing funding is a fundamental element of any co-creation endeavour. However, the funding of the future network which has evolved from a funding-secured and finite research project is a challenging task per se. In the case of LLs and RIs, challenges persist, particularly concerning the relatively novel nature of stakeholder cooperating methods for some funding institutions. This has resulted in LL approaches receiving less substantial funding compared to other research and innovation approaches. One solution to overcome being dependent on only external funders is to also charge members with a fee. To address this challenge effectively, it is essential to **emphasise the added value of the future network** for them and why it would be worth investing this fee to the network. Also, highlighting the need for financial resources of the network, such as for network coordination, is crucial to raise the acceptance of a potential fee. Another challenge lies in demonstrating this added value in comparison to other partnering networks, like ENoLL. The future network should include strengthened education activities on this topic, where applicable.

Another suggested avenue for a funding source is to involve regions more actively in funding initiatives. This approach can pique their interest, as it not only fosters place-based innovation but also enhances their image as forward-thinking regions.

The role of national and regional involvement extends beyond funding. They play a pivotal role in nurturing strong movements within their respective countries, commencing from grassroots initiatives and **expanding to influence institutions and the EU level**. This role aligns with a key driver of the transition to agroecology, which hinges on the development of institutional structures within the future network. Such structures are instrumental in building capacities and seamlessly integrating LLs and RIs into successful institutions. On a national level, the establishment of spaces for practical demonstration and peer-to-peer learning is essential. These spaces are instrumental in showcasing best practices and fostering a culture of collaboration and facilitation. Additionally, the active involvement of regional authorities within the future network can stimulate policy-making and regulatory changes, leading to a heightened understanding of regional agricultural knowledge.

4.2 Project management in the network

The experience of stakeholder engagement in the ALL-Ready project teaches us that multiple aspects of project management play an important role in the successful involvement and co-creation with stakeholders of the agroecology living lab and research infrastructure community. Important elements include: (1) appropriate time and budgetary resources planning for stakeholder engagement activities; (2) setting clear, feasible and flexible objectives, and clear roles; and (3) defining output and impact indicators to evaluate stakeholder engagement.

4.2.1 Resources planning

Focusing on time-related considerations for co-creation and stakeholder engagement activities shows the need for realistic timeframes, the underestimation of time requirements, and the potential for enhancing the quality of engagement outcomes by allocating more time. This is further influenced by resource-related challenges, particularly the budgetary constraints faced during the organisation of regional stakeholder engagement workshops. This emphasises the importance of aligning budgetary resources with the time demands of co-creation and engagement activities and highlights the need for additional resources to accommodate larger workshops and comprehensively cover regions that may have been less addressed.

(1) Time planning and allocation

Co-creation necessitates a substantial investment of time for effective stakeholder engagement. The future network is advised to consider establishing a **dedicated, realistic timeframe for co-creation and stakeholder engagement activities**. In the ALL-Ready project, there was a partial underestimation of the time needed for co-creation and stakeholder engagement across different work packages. This limitation impacted the potential for co-creation with pilot network members and broader engagement of additional LLs and RIS in the agroecology community. Allocating more time to individual activities could enhance the quality of engagement outcomes. For instance, pilot network members provided valuable inputs to WP6, supporting the redesign and refinement of the VRE to better meet their needs. However, additional time could have allowed for more iterations and increased engagement to enhance the quality of results, but this was constrained by time and budget considerations within the Coordination and Support Action (CSA). WP6 recommends weekly meetings with VRE users, adaptable to their availability, to prevent saturation and enhance engagement (WP6).

Furthermore, the project underestimated the time required for the network facilitator's co-creation activities within the pilot network, including the associated time intensity. **More time would have enabled more thoughtful consideration** of engagement methods, leading to more engaging meetings and activities (WP3). Given the challenges and time-consuming nature of co-creation in an international environment with multiple stakeholders, it is considered best practice to focus on less time-consuming co-designing activities with pilot network members. Moreover, with more time and fewer project delays (linked to collaboration demands from AE4EU), WP2 could have conducted a more comprehensive mapping exercise by involving stakeholders earlier and more frequently. Similarly, the regional workshops would have benefited from a longer timeframe than what was allocated in the ALL-Ready project, allowing for increased participation from stakeholders in similar regional workshops (WP4). It is crucial to acknowledge that identifying real-world solutions with stakeholders requires adequate time to transition from abstract discussions to practical solution-oriented talks (WP4). Additionally, due to time constraints, WP6 was unable to

involve individual users (researchers, policymakers, farmers, agribusinesses, and consumers/citizens) in the testing and co-creation of the VRE, primarily focusing on coordinators of LLs and RIs.

The facilitation of engagement activities also provides important insights. For instance, after the first pilot network meeting (December 2021), it became evident that **more frequent and longer breaks** between activities increased engagement during the sessions and allowed for peer-exchange and networking – a highly valued aspect for the members. To enable such breaks, it may be helpful to extend the duration of meetings or adjust the agenda to streamline the discussion of issues. Including a field trip for visiting LLs and RIs is valuable, with the optimal timing being in the middle of the meeting to ensure that exchange and reflection can continue after the field trip.

(2) Resource Allocation

Considering that stakeholder engagement demands a significant time investment, the availability of resources and financial budget posed a challenge in the ALL-Ready coordination and support action, particularly concerning the organisation of regional stakeholder engagement workshops. To ensure the success of stakeholder engagement in the future network, it is important to **align budgetary resources with the time required for co-creation** and engagement activities.

As the workshops within the future network are anticipated to be larger, accommodating up to 100 participants, this expectation must be accompanied by a **proportionally increased allocation of resources**. Ideally, more than four workshops per set should be considered to comprehensively cover regional concepts, including regions like the Baltic states that received limited coverage within the ALL-Ready project (WP4). This limitation was observed in the case of designing the VRE in WP6, which recognised the time-intensive nature of the co-creation process, emphasising the need for additional resources for its success within the future network. To effectively manage the time demands of engagement and co-creation within the future network, as well as to facilitate more frequent and higher-quality meetings, it is relevant to allocate a sufficient budget for qualified human resources.

4.2.2 Objective setting

To set the stage for the future network, **well-defined objectives and roles** are recommended for the operationalisation of stakeholder engagement activities.

In the experience of WP5, defining a more detailed action plan at the beginning of the project would have allowed to lay out the different activities and define the respective level of engagement (inform, consult, involve, co-create) to better guide stakeholder engagement in the work package. Pilot Network members further noted that they perceived it challenging to be faced by too many questions in meetings without clear action plan stating for which action their input is relevant. Furthermore, persons involved stated that the collaboration between WP6 and AE4EU on stakeholder engagement in data management was limited in success because of a lack of clear ambition and objectives. Defining clear objectives for stakeholder engagement activities early on is therefore recommended for the implementation of the future network. This also includes setting clear context and objectives at the beginning of the individual network meetings.

Moreover, objectives need to be realistic and feasible. For example, WP5 achieved its objectives at the level of LLs, whereas at the other levels, objectives may have been too ambitious considering the duration and resources in the ALL-Ready project. They further point out that particularly in agroecology, the amount and diversity of stakeholders makes this a challenging task.

On the other hand, flexibility is needed in designing and running the project and the future network. It is possible that approaches change. The adjustment of project objectives reflects that there is an impact of the activities undertaken with stakeholders (WP4, WP7). For instance, WP6 had to change the initially-defined roadmap because it made more sense to include the pilot network members instead of the work package leaders in the stakeholder engagement activities of the work package.

In addition to defining clear objectives, it is recommended to set clear roles in the implementation of stakeholder engagement activities. For instance, in the beginning of the ALL-Ready project, roles in WP5 were not very clearly defined. This made it difficult to define a clear action plan. In the first in person annual meeting in Paris in March 2022, WP5 agreed on a more structured framework for the capacity building plan and the focus was defined more clearly, focusing on the pilot members as main stakeholders.

4.2.3 Evaluation of stakeholder engagement

To establish a successful future network, a robust evaluation process is needed, which incorporates clear indicators to effectively monitor and assess stakeholder engagement activities within the network. Although the initial phases of the ALL-Ready project did not include a concrete evaluation plan, valuable insights from our stakeholder inquiry have illustrated the importance of implementing a participatory monitoring and evaluation approach.

The Pilot Network Meeting Report shows the positive response from the members when asked for their personal feedback. This response suggests that incorporating their expert knowledge and providing a sense of value and motivation can enhance the future network's output and overall quality. Additionally, interviews with WP leads have highlighted the need to monitor success, leading to the initial identification of both output and impact indicators for their respective stakeholder engagement activities.

Below, we present the preliminary indicators that we have inductively developed from the material collected (Table 2). We recommend further development of these indicators to establish a robust evaluation framework for the future network.

Table 2 First potential indicators to evaluate stakeholder engagement

Output indicators	Impact indicators
Achievement of planned activities	Continuous Mobilisation of internal and external stakeholders
Utilisation of project outputs by stakeholders	Achievement of building trust with stakeholders
Diversity of Stakeholder Participation	Network Sustainability and Growth
Activity level of stakeholders	Knowledge Dissemination and Uptake

(1) Output indicators

Output indicators are fundamental in measuring the immediate outcomes of our engagement activities. They serve as a baseline for developing more detailed output indicators for the future network.

A common output indicator observed in ALL-Ready stakeholder engagement activities is **the achievement of the planned activities**. This indicator can serve as a starting point for assessing the effectiveness of future network activities. WP leads have confirmed the achievement of stakeholder engagement objectives in their respective WPs, indicating a positive trend.

The **utilisation of project outputs by stakeholders** also serves as another significant indicator. For instance, the conceptual framework developed in WP1 has been applied in other contexts to analyse the requirements and importance of agroecology transition by actors like ENoLL. This framework empowers actors involved in the agroecology transition to measure their contributions effectively. Similarly, external stakeholders have gained increased knowledge and proficiency in agroecology and LL methods (WP2). The impact of the agroecology transition conceptual framework in WP1 was further measured by the reduced frequency of questions related to the definition of LLs, transition, and agroecology among external stakeholders after exposure to the framework. This indicator highlights the practical impact of our work.

The Diversity of Stakeholder Participation evaluates the variety and representation of stakeholder groups involved in network activities. It assesses whether a wide range of stakeholders, including those with different interests, expertise, and backgrounds, are actively participating in network events and initiatives. Metrics for this indicator might include:

- The representation of various stakeholder categories (e.g., farmers, researchers, policymakers, NGOs) in network activities.
- The inclusion of stakeholders from different geographic regions or sectors within the agroecology field.
- The engagement of stakeholders with varying levels of experience or expertise in agroecology and LLs.

Activity level of stakeholders evaluates the immediate outcomes of engagement activities. It assesses the level of participation and activity among stakeholders, reflecting their current engagement in network activities. It helps to gauge the extent to which stakeholders are actively participating in network activities, which is an important aspect of assessing the project's success. Increased interest and participation in regional workshops (WP4) and co-creation activities (WP6) indicated the effectiveness of our engagement efforts within ALL-Ready. The metrics could include their attendance and participation in e.g., workshops, response rate to emails, provision of inputs, and engagement with reports, minutes, and summaries.

(2) Impact indicators

Impact indicators go beyond immediate outputs and measure the broader effects of our engagement activities. Experiences from WP4 indicate that activities within the ALL-Ready project had multiple impacts on stakeholder engagement in the pilot network and the project as a whole. First, the regional workshops organised by WP4 were successful in bringing actors together and fostering valuable relationships among participants. Despite the availability of various workshops and networking opportunities in some regions, the workshops facilitated new linkages and relationships, indicating a clear benefit (WP4, WP2). Similarly, the development of the agroecology conceptual framework in WP1 effectively united different parties under a common project (WP1).

WP2's experiences indicate that ALL-Ready has **significantly mobilised both internal and external stakeholders**, paving the way for the Agroecology Partnership. Many ALL-Ready stakeholders are now involved in the Partnership, and external stakeholders have been reached, informed, and made aware of the Partnership. Some actors have gained additional skills and assumed leading roles, exemplified by ÖMKI, which will lead a work package in the future network—a role that might not have been possible before.

Evaluating the achievement of **building trust with stakeholders** can serve as another impact indicator. WP7 assesses the impact of communication and science-policy dialogue by the level of engagement with key stakeholders, particularly the SCAR Agroecology SWG, on an equal relationship basis. Building trust with stakeholders involved in the ALL-Ready pilot

network and the SCAR SWG has been a successful outcome of our stakeholder engagement activities.

Assessing **Network Sustainability and Growth** would be relevant to ensure a long-lasting network. This could include metrics like the expansion and development of the network's membership, its ability to secure funding for future projects, and its continued impact on agroecology research and practices.

Evaluation how **knowledge generated through the network has been disseminated and adopted** within the broader agricultural and scientific community. This could involve tracking the publication of research findings, the number of citations or references in academic literature, or the integration of agroecological concepts into educational curricula.

5. Highlighted lessons learnt and concluding thoughts

The lessons learnt from our stakeholder engagement experiences can provide a valuable input when building the future network. The lessons learnt were created by collecting feedback from a multitude of stakeholders of the ALL-Ready project, using previous deliverables, workshop reports, surveys, and semi-structured interviews. On one side, these lessons encompass insights drawn from the project level which can be translated into the more operational sphere of the future network. This includes learnings on stakeholder identification, the timing and methods of engagement, the content of activities, and the nuances of communication. On the other side, we drew lessons learnt from the network level, which relate more to strategic sphere of the future network. This domain includes crucial considerations such as the governance structure and size, as well as nuanced project management approaches.

Four equally relevant lessons learnt are particularly important for successful stakeholder engagement. While these four lessons stand out as the most salient and applicable for our future network, the other lessons also offer valuable insights into the complexities and challenges of stakeholder engagement, as well as the opportunities and benefits of collaboration. Therefore, we recommend considering and incorporating these other lessons as well, as they provide additional guidance and support for the future network's objectives.

Our selection process was guided by four criteria which took into account:

- Stakeholder feedback,
- demonstrated improvements,
- relevance to our future network,
- and likeliness of impact.

Taking into account these criteria, we aimed to highlight a lesson that resonated with our stakeholders' perspectives and expectations, reinforcing the significance of their input. We also prioritised a lesson that showcased demonstrated tangible improvement over time, offering concrete examples of how we applied these insights and observed positive changes in our engagement approaches. This commitment to continuous improvement underscores the value of learning from experience. Furthermore, we gave particular prominence to a lesson that exhibited a clear and significant impact on stakeholder engagement in our specific context. The measurable outcomes associated with these lessons strengthened their standing in our conclusion, making it more compelling and relevant. In essence, our selection process ensured that the lessons featured here are not only informed by stakeholder feedback and marked by demonstrated improvement but are also directly pertinent to the future network and hold tangible impacts on our engagement practices.

Lesson 1: Tailoring Content to Stakeholder Needs Drives Optimal Engagement

Aligning network activities' content with members' specific needs and preferences is of central importance for successful stakeholder engagement, as it supports higher engagement and meaningful collaborations. Stakeholders emphasise that the well-aligned content of activities fosters meaningful connections and drives engagement. Our pilot network evaluation survey revealed the pressing need to further highlight practical applications of agroecology within capacity-building activities. To address this, we recommend that capacity-building sessions include real-world examples from the context where they are taking place. Tailoring content to the unique needs of LLs and RIs is also essential, considering stakeholders' distinct preferences. Diverse participation within LLs highlights the need for tailored content. To ensure that stakeholder interests and perspectives are well represented,

it is important to engage representatives from key stakeholder groups in the planning of content.

Lesson 2: Effective Communication Strategies Enhance External Stakeholder Engagement

Successful external stakeholder engagement relies on effective communication. Throughout the project we observed a tangible improvement in our approach to communicate with external stakeholders. As the project progressed, the value of employing clear and accessible terminology, a context-specific and relevant tone, and a well-structured communication strategy became evident. Our experience has taught us the importance of improving communication with external stakeholders about the future network by applying the following recommendations. Overall, a well-defined communication strategy is crucial which includes the planning of dissemination activities more effectively. This entails assigning communication tasks to partners, leveraging network members as ambassadors, and allocating sufficient resources as key strategies. Additionally, reaching and engaging new external stakeholders can be improved by avoiding specialised or technical terminology; for example, describing the sometimes-unknown term of agroecology as 'green transition in agriculture' has proven to be more accessible. Further, regional nuances in agroecology and general stakeholder interests require context-specific messaging. This can be achieved by using concrete examples, and clear metrics to encourage greater participation. In conclusion, our improved communication approach emphasises the importance of clarity, resonance, and strategic planning in engaging stakeholders across the future network.

Lesson 3: The Value of Robust Evaluation in Stakeholder Engagement

Prioritising a well-structured evaluation process is of significant value. This lesson emerged from our project's experience, highlighting the need for clear indicators to monitor and evaluate stakeholder engagement activities effectively within the network. Initially, the project did not plan for a concrete evaluation process. However, insights from stakeholder inquiries revealed the opportunity to implement a participatory monitoring and evaluation approach. This approach resonated positively with members, as their feedback added value and motivation, enhancing the quality of our network's output. Both output and impact indicators were identified to facilitate the evaluation process. Output indicators include the achievement of engagement objectives and the utilisation of project outputs by stakeholders. Impact indicators encompass the positive impacts of stakeholder engagement, such as fostering valuable relationships, mobilising stakeholders, and building trust. In conclusion, this lesson emphasises the importance of effective monitoring and evaluation practices, providing a foundation for continuous improvement and ensuring the success of the future network.

Lesson 4: Adaptable Engagement Formats for Enhanced Stakeholder Involvement

This particular lesson stands out due to its significant relevance for our project's success. Based on experience in the project, we note that diverse engagement formats allow flexibility so that each activity can best respond to the objective set for the activity and the target audience. If the format is aligned with the specific context, stakeholder type, desired level of participation (and accessibility), this can facilitate better engagement and active participation. In terms of preferred formats, stakeholders in general expressed a preference for hands-on sessions with co-creation tools and methods, webinars, practical exercises, and field visits. Stakeholders appreciated opportunities to connect with other scientists and build future research consortia during these events. It is relevant to note, however, that online meetings, while convenient, accessible, and very important during the COVID pandemic restrictions, did pose challenges. Stakeholders felt less connected and faced barriers to participation. Iterations partially compensated for the limitations of online meetings. In-person meetings, on the other hand, allowed for more comprehensive discussions, but the digital format enabled regular meetings without traveling during the pandemic. Given their different advantages and disadvantages, a balance between online and in-person activities

is desired. It is important that the facilitators of the process proactively identify and address potential barriers to engagement, which may include time constraints, inadequate inclusion, and method complexity. Balancing professionalism and enjoyment during sessions fosters an engaging and comfortable atmosphere.

By focusing on **Lesson 1**, we can ensure that the future network activities are designed with a clear understanding of stakeholders' needs and preferences. This will not only enhance the relevance and effectiveness of the engagement efforts but also foster meaningful connections and higher levels of engagement. **Lesson 2** recalls the importance of clear and accessible communication. While moving forward, we need continue to refine the communication strategies to ensure that we effectively convey the value and goals of the future network. This will enable more successful engagement of external stakeholders and build stronger relationships. **Lesson 3** underscores the need for a robust evaluation process within the future network. By prioritising clear indicators and participatory monitoring and evaluation, one can continuously assess and improve the stakeholder engagement activities. This commitment to evaluation will ensure that the future network remains responsive and effective. **Lesson 4**, with its focus on adaptable engagement formats, is particularly relevant for the future. One needs to consider the specific context, stakeholder types, and accessibility when designing engagement activities. This flexibility will help overcome potential barriers and cater to diverse preferences, ensuring active stakeholder involvement.

In conclusion, applying these lessons is not just a matter of improving our practices; it is important for the success and sustainability of our future network. By tailoring content, communicating effectively, prioritizing evaluation, and embracing adaptable formats, we can create a network that truly engages stakeholders, builds trust, and achieves its objectives. Our commitment to implementing these lessons will be a guiding force behind our network's continued growth and impact.

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7. Appendices

Appendix A Process of a content structuring content analysis, by Kuckartz and Rädiker, 2019

Source: Höppner et al., 2022

Appendix B Evaluation survey of the regional workshop

Goal of this survey:

With this short survey we would like to understand your experience of the workshop. Your answers will be treated anonymously and will only be used for evaluating 'stakeholder engagement activities' organised within the time frame of this project ALL-Ready. The results will be used to improve our future activities. Your insights and experiences will be shared within our consortium and included in an overall report summarising our 'stakeholder engagement activities' (anonymously).

Thank you very much!!

The ALL-Ready Team

- What kind of initiative do you represent?
 - Living Lab
 - Research Infrastructure
 - Other
 - If other please explain

- What kind of organisation do you represent?
 - Farming
 - Value chain
 - Research
 - NGO
 - Foundation
 - Government, public authorities, and administration
 - Other
 - If other, please explain

- Are you mainly active at:
 - European level
 - National level
 - Regional level
 - Local level
 - Combination of the above

- Based on the information provided to you before the workshop, was there a clear added value for you to participate in the workshop presented? If yes, which one?

- Did you feel comfortable to express your opinion during the workshop?

Yes/No; Please explain why.

- When the workshop started, were the objectives of the meeting and your role clearly stated to you.
Yes / No, If No, could you please explain what was unclear?

- Did you feel actively involved during the event/workshop?

Yes/No; How?

- Did you have the opportunity to interact with other participating stakeholders during the workshop?

Yes/No; How?

- Was there enough time to express your views and pose questions?
Yes / No? If not, which questions would you have liked to pose and discuss?

- Did the workshop meet your expectations? Why or why not?

- Do you have the feeling that the workshop was useful to you? Why? Why not?

- Do you have any suggestions to improve the workshop?

- How was your experience with 'receiving information about the future European network' so far?

- I received enough information about the future network
 - I would like to receive more information
 - I am overwhelmed by the amount of information
- Concerning a future European network of Agroecology LLs and RIs, would you like to be a member of the future network? Why or why not?

Appendix C Evaluation survey of the pilot network

1. Participation in the ALL-Ready network

- Is it the first time you have participated in such a network?
- Why did you decide to participate in the Pilot Network?
- Think back to when you agreed to join. Is this what you expected? Was it better/worse?
- Did it feel like you were part of a "network"? Why/why not?
- How would you define the participation of your organization in the pilot network?
 - a. You are/feel informed, you receive(d) information about it
 - b. You are/feel consulted, your input has been asked (but you are not aware how and whether your input is actually used in further preparation)
 - c. You are/feel involved, you gave/give feedback and this is taking into account in the further preparation of the future network
 - d. You feel you are co-creating with the people preparing the network and with other LLs and RIs in the network, you are deciding together how some of the aspects of the future network are going to be organised, e.g., the capacity building, the governance,
 - e. None of these. Please explain.
- Were you satisfied with the level of integration between the ALL-Ready project and the pilot network? How do you see your role in the pilot network?
- In your experience, what worked well in the management of the pilot network in general? What was your highlight? In your experience, what did not work so well?
- How does the Pilot Network (or the ALL-Ready project) benefit your organisation? Is there a potential for using/integrating the outcomes of the pilot network co-creation activities (e.g., Virtual Lab, capacity building items, used co-creation tools, etc.) in your LL/RI work?
- What did you learn from participating in the network?
- Were the explanations/communication materials sufficient to help you quickly understand what the network was all about? And what AE LLs are all about? How could these be improved?
- In your experience, how well was information shared in the network so far?
- What were your impressions about the co-design process of the capacity building programme? (workshops, trainings, facilitation)
- What were your impressions about the co-creation process of the pilot network activities (workshops, action planning, learning roundtables)? How can the next pilot network meeting be improved?
- What were your impressions about the co-construction process of Future Network's Implementation Plan (workshops, facilitation)?
- What were your impressions about the co-design process of the Virtual Lab (workshops, tests, trainings, etc.)?

- What were your impressions about the co-creation process of the pilot network activities (workshops, action planning, learning roundtables, etc.)?
- How can the next pilot network meeting be improved?

2. Involvement in the future European network

- Reflecting on the different tools developed in ALL READY (the framework for agroecology transition, the capacity building programme, the virtual lab, the implementation plan), which one do you think will be the most valuable for the future network?
- Is the difference between the future network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures and the future partnership of Agroecology clear to you? How do you understand their respective objectives?
- Will you be interested in being involved in the future network?
- If yes, what benefits do you see for your organisation?
- Does the network need something in particular? What resources would you be willing to / able to dedicate to the network? Why / why not?
- How satisfied were you with the time commitment and frequency of meetings with respect to the pilot network? What are your expectations for the future network?
- What would you say to another organisation considering joining the future network?
- Do you have any other suggestions?

Appendix D Interview guideline with WP leads

Context

Stakeholder engagement is a crucial part of the ALL-Ready project as all work packages are built upon input from stakeholders at regional, national, and European level. Therefore, we will have to get an overview of whom these stakeholders are and how to involve them.

ILVO will support the different work packages in defining and reaching these stakeholders as ILVO is task leader for the approach of setting up a stakeholder engagement plan (task 3.1 WP3: stakeholder engagement coordination).

Therefore, ILVO would like to achieve a deep understanding of the WP leaders' expectations and interpretations of the involvement of stakeholders. Each work package has its own objectives and type of stakeholders to involve with the appropriate strategy to reach them. To achieve optimal results for each task/WP it is important to carefully design the stakeholder engagement process.

Once we have gained input from the WP leaders, we would like to engage with the AE4EU project and the SCAR and/or EC representatives to understand their expectations as well.

Approach

ILVO proposes to conduct **1 online interview (90') with each WP leader**. For the sake of efficiency, we have prepared some questions for the WP leaders to read and think through. We will use this list to structure our conversation. It is **not** the idea to write the answers down and send them back to us.

List of questions for the interview

1. Identify WP objectives (what)

1. Describe the main objectives of your work package.
2. Describe step-by-step how you intended to achieve those objectives in the work package. What approach did you follow? How was the timing?

2. What is your objective in engaging stakeholders? (why)

1. In the beginning it may have been difficult to define objectives for stakeholder engagement. What were these difficulties? What contributed to the difficulties? Could something has been done differently to define objectives? Is it just time?
2. Based on your experience, what can you say now on why it is important to engage stakeholders in your WP? Please explain.

3. Identify stakeholders that need to be engaged in the WP (who and why them?)

If we consider the objectives of the WP, we want you to think about the stakeholders/stakeholder groups you involved

- Policy makers (national, regional, European)
- Scientists

- Advisors
 - Experts on ... agroecology, living labs, etc
 - Practitioners (LL, AE, education)
 - NGOs
 - civil society organisations
 - Agricultural organisations
 - National contact points
 - Existing networks (e. g. Agroecology Europe)
 - AE4EU
1. Which stakeholders were influenced by the outcome or output of your WP?
 2. What stakeholder groups might have an influence/power on how your WP and actions developed?
 3. How did you identify representatives for each of these stakeholder groups?
 4. How do you know whether you have included all relevant stakeholders?

4. Identify strategies to engage stakeholders during WP activities (how? And when?)

Now that we have a more global view on who to involve, we can get in more detail at when and how to involve them or a selection of them.

1. What level of engagement did you foresee for these different stakeholder groups (differentiate between different levels of engagement: collaborate, consult, empower, inform, involve) and why?
2. At what point in your step-by-step plan did you want to involve these stakeholders?
3. What format did you use for involving the stakeholders at each of these steps? Why?
 - Questionnaires
 - Workshops
 - Interviews
 - Newsletters
 - Platform on the website
4. Which representatives of stakeholder groups were reached?
 - National contact points
 - Project partners
 - EC

○ ...

5. How many representatives of the different stakeholder groups were contacted? All of them, a selection? Why?

Evaluation of your activities

Keeping in mind your experience so far, with you WP and with the ALL-Ready project as a whole:

1. Did you reach the WP objectives for stakeholder engagement?
2. Was the approach you used appropriate for reaching the WP objectives? The overall ALL-Ready project objectives?
3. What are the consequences/shortcomings of the method you used to engage stakeholders?
4. What works well in reaching different stakeholder groups? Why?
5. When is the best time to engage? Why?
6. What would you have done differently?
7. What are your key lessons learnt from engaging stakeholders?
8. Were there missed opportunities and groups that were not reached at all (at the WP level and at the project level)? Is this a problem? Please explain.

Appendix E Level of participation for each of the stakeholder groups (Source: D3.1)

Stakeholder group @EU level	Appropriate level of participation					
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
SCAR AE working group	Inform/collaborate		Inform	Inform / consult / collaborate	Involve	Inform
AE4EU	Collaborate		Involve	Collaborate	Involve	Collaborate
EAB	Involve		Involve	Consult / involve	Involve	Consult
Research	Inform, collaborate		Consult/involve	Consult / involve	Involve	
European Commission	Involve		Involve	Involve	Involve	
Value chain actors	Involve		Inform	Consult / involve	Involve	
NGO's	Involve		Inform	Consult / involve	Consult	
Farmers' unions	Involve		Inform	Consult / involve	Consult	
AE related Networks	Involve		Consult	Consult / involve	Consult	
AKIS	Consult/collaborate		Inform	Consult / involve	Consult	
Stakeholder group @national level	Appropriate level of participation					
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
Research	Consult	Consult	Consult/involve	Consult / collaborate	Involve	
Policy makers/national authorities	Inform	Consult	Collaborate	Collaborate	Involve	
Value chain actors	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve	
NGO's	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve	
Farm advisors	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Involve	
AKIS	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	consult	
Farmers' unions	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	Consult	
Consumer associations	Inform		Inform	Inform / consult	consult	
Stakeholder group @local/regional level	Appropriate level of participation					
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
Researchers	Inform		Involve	Inform / consult	Involve	

Policy makers	Inform	Collaborate	Involve / collaborate	Involve
Value chain actors	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
NGO's	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
Farm advisors	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
AKIS	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Consult
Farmers and farmers' unions	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Involve
Representatives of LLs and RIs (pilot network)	Involve	Involve	Involve / collaborate	Collaborate Collaborate
Citizens movements	Inform	Inform	Inform / consult	Involve